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HONEY BEES SURVIVING *VARROA DESTRUCTOR* INFESTATIONS
IN THE WORLD: LESSONS WE CAN TAKE

*Le api mellifere resistenti alle infestazioni di Varroa destructor nel mondo:
quali indicazioni possiamo trarre*

When *Varroa destructor* invaded France in 1982, feral colonies disappeared and were destroyed by the mite. In 1994, few feral colonies could be observed back in different places, especially in the west of France. An experiment was designed to look at natural selection and survival of those colonies. Since they were still alive in 1999, we evaluated the surviving of other varroa untreated honey bee colonies. We collected about 70 colonies which were varroa untreated for at least 3 years from different places in France. Those colonies survived about 8 years to the mite, some of them being untreated for 14 years. In Avignon, we studied the population dynamics of those bees compared to hybrid control susceptible bees and showed a significantly lower number of mites in the tolerant colonies.

Different hypotheses can explain this phenomenon. Honey bees could have become resistant to the mite. The mite could have evolved toward a less virulence to the bees. The bees could be more resistant to viruses associated with the presence of the mite, or a co-evolution between those actors in their typical biotopes could have been favoured. Beekeeping management could also explain it. We did test those different hypotheses as the search of varroa resistance traits associated with this survival can be helpful for selecting honey bees against the mite. Chemical communication and genomics were interesting tools to understand this phenomenon and to select bees.

Since, we still keep those varroa surviving honey bee populations and others have been found or naturally selected in different parts of the world. The mechanisms of this tolerance are partly known and will be discussed in

the framework of honey bee selection and beekeeping, as well as the interest to keep naturally varroa surviving bees.

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